

Recommendation 15:

Using '*Digitalization*' to meet the public sector need '*Increase resource productivity*'

Actual solutions and services:

Digital transformation promises great things for the public sector and the citizens it serves, from lower costs and greater efficiency to real-time services, seamless communication and enhanced program effectiveness. Shared services, greater collaboration and integration, improved fraud management and productivity enhancements enable system-wide efficiencies.

We can mention as an example:

- STORK project
- PAE (Portal Administracion electronica)
- Cita Previa de Atención Primaria (online medical appointment)
- Agencia Tributaria

SWOT Analysis

Strengths

- **Offering more communication and transaction channels**
- **Convenience – enabling access through a digital device**
- **Flexibility in manipulating information**
- **Innovation**
- **Scalability**
- **Speed of doing business**

Weaknesses

- High initial investment and maintenance costs
- Availability of digital equipment (e.g. computer) needed
- Digital literacy and competence needed both in the back-office and in the front desk

Opportunities

- **Digitalisation of public services**
- **Use of electronic files and electronic records**
- **24/7 services availability**
- **Increased system interoperability**
- **Information and service reuse**
- **Economies of scale enabled.**

Threats

- Changes required in both processes and IT systems of the public sector
- Digital illiteracy of public sector employees and citizens
- Resistance to change
- Security and vulnerability threats

Increase resource productivity:

Frugally utilise available resources (to do more with less) and manage their movement across the public sector in an efficient manner (especially in this era of constrained resources). The sub needs under this header include: fairer distribution of resources, lack of resources, working without budgets, secondment of resources across departments. Our informants expressed their voices as, "Ensure the appropriate resources for the services offered", "Ensure sustainability of the actions and projects undertaken" and "Resources should be sufficient and transferable across departments"

Digitalization:

*Digitalization corresponds the process of the technologically-induced change, whereas digital transformation is described as the total and overall societal effect of digitalization. In a narrower sense, digitalization as well as digital transformation may refer to the concept of "going paperless". **

* Gartner IT Glossary – Digitalization, <http://www.gartner.com/it-glossary/digitalization/>
Wikipedia – Digital transformation, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Digital_transformation